

CreaSTEAM' schools Dissemination

School's own dissemination process through news on their websites, promotional videos and presentations within their social sphere:

- <https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=214416463878753>
- <http://www.italiannetwork.it/news.aspx?id=64605>
- <https://www.cbcs-lollar.de/2021/06/01/clemens-for-future-klaert-auf/>
- <http://www.scuolamausiliatriceroma.org/scuola-secondaria-di-ii-grado/progetto-erasmus-creasteam/>
- <http://www.agora.grial.eu/news/primera-reuni%C3%B3n-presencial-del-proyecto-creasteam>
- <https://www.agensir.it/quotidiano/2021/1/15/scuola-fidae-al-via-il-progetto-erasmus-creasteam-kaladich-presidente-guardiamo-alleuropa-senza-frontiere/>
- <https://www.fidae.it/al-via-il-progetto-erasmus-co-thinking-and-creation-for-steam-diversity-gap-reduction-fidae-e-nella-partnership-europea/>
- <https://twitter.com/bursaimemerge/status/1447474176609116163?s=20>
- <https://www.salleurl.edu/en/research/project/creasteam>

